

scald resistance.

An early step was to identify a suitable culture medium that would enhance growth and abundant sporulation of the fungus. For all isolations, portions of leaf tissue from the advancing margin of scald lesions were treated with 0.5% NaO Cl for 2 minutes then rinsed several times in sterile distilled water. Several attempts were initially unsuccessful in isolating *R. oryzae* from leaves of susceptible rice cultivars with typical scald lesions, using commercial potato dextrose agar (PDA) pH 6 in 9-cm plastic petri dishes on laboratory benches at room temperature (23-25° C). However, sucrose agar (SA) pH 7, and peptone agar (PA) pH 5 were used successfully

under the same conditions. On transfer from either SA or PA, the fungus was still not sustained on PDA. In addition to those media, 4 other media were tested. V-8 vegetable juice agar (VA) pH 4.3 was the most successful in maintaining good growth and abundant sporulation of *R. oryzae*.

To determine possible sources of inoculum, *R. oryzae* was isolated from 2 of 25 water droplets that had been sitting on scald lesions for about 2 hours following a rain shower in the morning in several field plots planted with ROK 16. The fungus was isolated from 2 out of 200 1-year-old seeds and 59 out of 100 freshly harvested ones of ROK 16. Fungal colonies on PA also formed

from plating out soil collected from rice fields during the growing season and transferred to VA. *R. oryzae* was not detected in the limited number of soil assays conducted.

The preliminary results indicate that the Sierra Leone isolate of *R. oryzae* does not grow well, if at all, on PDA; under Sierra Leone conditions seed, not soil, might be important in spreading the disease; rain splash contributes to short-distance spread of the fungus. More detailed work to verify these observations, as well as quantitative approaches to growth and sporulation in VA and other media and on primary sources of inoculum, is planned. ■

Seed discoloration disease and its chemical control

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Discoloration of rice grain is a minor fungal disease. Until recently, it has been prevalent in all parts of Thailand.

Infected panicles are covered with brown to dark brown lesions. The disease is distinct from blast because no lesions are formed on the neck and nodes. Grains may be infected by various organisms before or after harvest. Infected plants have partially filled discolored grains, which have reduced viability and quality.

Ten fungi were isolated from infected panicles of diseased plants collected from naturally infected fields. Some fungi individually were able to cause

seed discoloration. Characteristic symptoms of each on the glumes follow:

1. *Helminthosporium oryzae* caused brown spots with collapsed centers on the surface. In severe cases, the entire glume surface turned brown.
2. *Trichoconis padwickii* caused pale brown to whitish spots with a relatively dark-brown border on the glumes.
3. *Fusarium semitectum* caused purplish brown to reddish brown discoloration.
4. *Cercospora oryzae* caused purplish brown streaks that were longer than those of brown spot on the glume.
5. *Acrocyndrium oryzae* and *Curvularia lunata* caused serious discoloration and empty grains.

When the panicle was inoculated with a mixed inoculum of several fungi, typical symptoms incited by the individual incitants showed together on the same plants.

A two-set field experiment on chemical control of the disease was conducted at the Rice Pathology Branch, Bangkhen, Bangkok, in 1980. The experiment had a randomized, complete block design with three replications. Seven fungicides — copper oxychloride, MBC + mancozeb, mancozeb, edifenphos, Polyoxin Z, Sisthane, and carboxin — were sprayed on susceptible RD9 variety at heading. On one set of plants — for disease prevention — the fungicides were sprayed once directly onto the newly emerged panicle 2 days before artificial inoculation. On the other set — for curative efficacy — the fungicides were sprayed once onto the panicle 7 days after artificial inoculation.

To evaluate the results, 20 panicles were collected randomly from each plot for examination of diseased seeds. The seeds per panicle in each treatment were counted and classified as healthy, dirty, and empty seeds. The data were statistically analyzed.

Table 1. Effectiveness of chemicals in preventing rice seed discoloration.^a Bangkok, Thailand.

Treatment	Dose (a.i./ha)	Total seeds per panicle	Healthy seeds per panicle	Dirty seeds per panicle	Empty seeds per panicle
Control	0	141.33 a	72.16 ab	60.86 c	8.31 a
Copper oxychloride	0.5 kg	143.00 a	57.61 a	79.18 d	6.21 a
MBC + mancozeb	0.75 kg	119.10 a	75.21 ab	37.93 ab	5.96 a
Mancozeb	0.75 kg	129.41 a	70.33 ab	52.83 bc	6.25 a
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	127.43 a	76.91 abc	45.00 ab	5.52 a
Polyoxin Z	1.5 kg	145.18 a	97.95 c	37.15 a	10.08 a
Sisthane	1 liter	144.56 a	90.61 bc	44.83 ab	9.12 a
Carboxin	1.75 liters	141.53 a	72.46 ab	62.68 c	6.38 a
CV		9.3%	15.08%	15.7%	28.5%

^aMeans followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Table 2. Curative efficacy of certain chemicals for rice seed discoloration.^a Bangkok, Thailand.

Treatment	Dose (a.i./ha)	Total seeds per panicle	Healthy seeds per panicle	Dirty seeds per panicle	Empty seeds per panicle
Control	0	120.81 a	56.45 a	54.26 a	10.10 a
Copper oxychloride	0.5 kg	94.33 a	48.61 a	36.95 a	8.77 a
MBC + mancozeb	0.75 kg	128.18 a	69.71 a	49.13 a	9.34 a
Mancozeb	0.75 kg	94.13 a	51.35 a	34.41 a	8.37 a
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	103.93 a	52.45 a	42.70 a	8.18 a
Polyoxin Z	1.5 kg	95.51 a	54.01 a	34.33 a	7.17 a
Sisthane	1 liter	99.13 a	58.71 a	32.01 a	8.41 a
Carboxin	1.75 liters	106.66 a	69.48 a	25.98 a	11.20 a
CV		15.0%	26.56%	38.0%	48.4%

^a Means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Plants treated with Polyoxin Z gave the highest number of healthy seeds (97.95) per panicle, followed by Sisthane with 90.61, and edifenphos with 76.91. Plants treated with copper oxychloride

had the lowest number of healthy seeds (57.61) per panicle, which was lower than that from the control plot. Copper oxychloride, which caused the highest number of dirty seeds (79.18) per pani-

cle, may be toxic to the panicle (Table 1).

No fungicide showed ability to cure the disease or decrease damage (Table 2). ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Dimorphopterus similis Slater (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae: Blissinae), a new rice pest from Nigeria

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During a recent survey of rice pests in Sokoto State, Nigeria, a large population of *Dimorphopterus similis* was encountered in rice stubble after harvest. The presence of this species in large numbers (av: 16 adult *D. similis* /hill) and complete failure of crops (yield about 50 kg/ha, or 3% of the 1974 average productivity for Africa) indicate that *D. similis* may become a major rice pest in Nigeria, and elsewhere.

Six species of Blissinae have been reported on rice *Oryza sativa*: *Blissus richardsoni* Drake from Cuba (Bruner et al 1945), *B. insularis* Barber from St. Croix (Wolcott 1936), *Ischnodemus congoensis* Slater from S. Rhodesia (Slater 1964a); *I. diplachne* Slater and Harrington from S. Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe) (Slater and Harrington 1970); *I. perplexus* Slater and Harrington from Senegal (Slater and Harrington 1970); and *Cavelerius excavatus* (Distant) from India (Fletcher 1921). This report, therefore, brings the

number found on rice to seven. It is also the first report of a species of *Dimorphopterus* with economic potential. This is interesting because *Dimorphopterus* is evidently the Old World ecological equivalent of the western hemisphere's *Blissus*, several species of which have economic importance (Hamid and Slater 1979). In view of the above and to facilitate further studies, we have summarized the present knowledge about *D. similis*.

This species originally was described from a single female from South Africa. It was next reported from Senegal and Nigeria. Host plants previously were unknown, although the specimens reported from Nigeria were collected on *Hyparrhenia involucreata* Stapf. (Gramineae). All reports from Africa, including the present one, were from grassland regions.

D. similis is one of 35 species presently included in the genus *Dimorphopterus*. These are distributed mainly in the Ethiopian (16), Oriental (10), and Palearctic (7) regions, but two species also extend into Australia.

The taxonomic status of a number of species of *Dimorphopterus*, including *D. similis*, is not satisfactorily established. This species is closely related to *D. nubicus*, *D. brachypterus*, and *D. graminum*, all reported from Nigeria. It

is desirable to study *D. similis* and its closest taxa to more satisfactorily establish their relationship. ■

Effect of potash levels on the incidence of rice whorl maggot

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Earlier work on the correlation between potash level and the occurrence of the rice whorl maggot showed that up to 135 kg potassium/ha had no effect on the maggot.

A trial conducted during the 1978-79 samba season (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec) at PES, Tirur, used higher levels of K than

Effect of potash levels on whorl maggot damage. 1978-79 samba season, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India.

K (kg/ha)	Damaged tillers ^a (%) 30 DT ^b
0	13.9 a
25	14.8 a
50	14.1 a
75	14.2 a
100	16.6 ab
125	16.3 ab
150	18.1 ab
175	20.8 b
200	24.2 b
CD	5R

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Days after transplanting.